

Citation for the Presentation of the
2011 ICPE Medal to

**THE LADY CATS,
Japan**

Presented at the
World Conference on Physics Education,
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In recognition of their excellent and sustained efforts to communicate physics through innovative hands-on experiments, the International Commission on Physics Education takes pleasure in awarding the ICPE Medal for 2011 to the LADY CATS.

The LADY CATS (LADY Creators of Activities for Teaching Science) is an organization of mainly, though not exclusively, female teachers from all levels of the educational system in Japan - from primary school to university. They are dedicated to the production and presentation of simple and inexpensive, yet beautiful, science experiments that demonstrate physics principles. Through their activities and passion they have engaged and excited students and teachers who have not been previously interested in physics. The LADY CATS aim especially to meet the challenge of countering the discomfort felt by many primary teachers when called on to teach physics. In Japan, many of these teachers are women who only have a background in general science. These teachers often feel unprepared for teaching physics-based topics. By their nature, the LADY CATS are particularly well suited to the task of inspiring and encouraging these primary teachers with an appreciation of physics.

The LADY CATS were founded in 2005. Since then, they have become widely known through their publications and their many appearances at international meetings, including several ICPE conferences. However, their work builds on that of an earlier Japanese teacher group known as the STRAY CATS. Together, these two groups have been sharing their unique approach to hands-on and minds-on physics education throughout the world for well over twenty years. Today, in honouring the LADY CATS, we honour also the tradition that gave rise to them. For this reason we invite Professor Hiroshi Kawakatsu who has been active in both groups to accept the 2011 ICPE Medal on behalf of the LADY CATS.

Robert Lambourne
Chairman of ICPE